

Z

hdk

Zürcher Hochschule der Künste

**Zurich
University
of the Arts**

**CoARA
Action Plan**

CoARA objectives and principles

The Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA) provides a framework for reforming how research and researchers are assessed. It aims to make evaluation practices more responsible, inclusive and supportive of high-quality research. Central to CoARA is to move beyond traditional metrics, such as journal impact factors or publication counts, to recognize the diverse contributions of researchers.

CoARA advocates for a qualitative, holistic approach to assessment. This includes valuing a wide range of research outputs (e.g. open data, software, policy papers, artistic works), as well as teaching, mentoring, teamwork and engagement beyond academia. It emphasizes transparency and integrity in evaluation, with clear criteria and informed peer review forming the basis of decisions. Equality, diversity, equity and inclusiveness are deemed essential: Assessment should recognize different roles, disciplines, and career stages, as well as reward collaborative and open practices. Institutions are encouraged to create supportive environments for different career paths and stages, ensuring that talent development and recognition are fair and sustainable.

Finally, CoARA emphasizes shared responsibility and continuous improvement. Institutions that sign the agreement commit to aligning their policies and practices with these principles, to experimenting with new approaches, and to sharing experiences with others. Progress is expected to be iterative, leaving room for learning and adaptation, yet always guided by the overarching aim: to advance research quality and integrity by reforming how contributions are valued and rewarded.

In practice, the ten CoARA Commitments can be summarized in four central areas of action:

- **Reforming assessment criteria and processes:** Gradually replace the reliance on journal- and publication-based metrics with broader, qualitative evaluation methods.
- **Recognizing diverse contributions:** Value the whole range of research outputs, activities and career paths.
- **Building a supportive culture:** Establish institutional conditions that support diversity, equity, and inclusivity, while strengthening the skills and awareness of evaluators and researchers.
- **Ensuring transparency and accountability:** Implement clear policies, monitor progress, and regularly share practices and experiences with the broader research community.

Together, these commitments provide a roadmap for universities and research organizations to develop a more balanced assessment culture. Moreover, CoARA has developed into a strong and influential body of advocacy across Europe and its national and European funding bodies.

ZHdK Focus

Zurich University of the Arts (ZHdK) has been a member of the Coalition on Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA) since October 2024. By joining CoARA, ZHdK commits itself to further develop, reform and review its research assessment criteria and processes based on the Action Plan.

The Action Plan is based on ZHdK's fundamental culture of qualitative assessment strategies. As a university of the arts, ZHdK conducts not only "classical" scientific research and artistic-scientific research but also artistic research, that is, research with, for and through art. Therefore, CoARA's emphasis on complementing quantitative metrics with qualitative metrics resonates strongly with ZHdK's research culture. By joining CoARA, ZHdK can actively engage in the ongoing transformation of the research-assessment culture and share its practices with the international community.

Therefore, Commitments 3 ("Abandon inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal- and publication-based metrics, in particular inappropriate uses of Journal Impact Factor (JIF) and h-index") and 10 ("Evaluate practices, criteria and tools based on solid evidence and the state-of-the-art in research on research, and make data openly available for evidence gathering and research") are of particular relevance to ZHdK. Its research output with, for and through the arts often takes non-traditional or linear forms such as exhibitions, performances, or practice-based projects. For this reason, conventional metrics such as the Journal Impact Factor or h-index already play a limited role in evaluating contributions in the arts.

By explicitly abandoning their inappropriate use (Commitment 3), ZHdK can further align its assessment culture with the diversity and specificity of artistic research. At the same time, focusing on evidence-based evaluation practices (Commitment 10) ensures that its criteria and tools remain robust, transparent and aligned with international developments in research assessment. This dual focus enables ZHdK to strengthen the credibility, inclusiveness and recognition of artistic research while also contributing to the broader transformation of research assessment.

ZHdK Action Plan

The current Action Plan was created in collaboration with the Research Affairs Committee, which consists of representatives from all ZHdK departments, as well as in collaboration with representatives from other organisational units, such as the Teaching Office, the Office for International Affairs and the Quality Management Unit. Actively involving these different units in establishing ZHdK's Action Plan ensures that the Plan is based on university-wide consensus. It also ensures that the key actors responsible for implementing the CoARA commitments are on board from the outset.

We have identified eight actions which we plan to achieve until 2029. However, the Action Plan is a "living document" and therefore adjustments to the Action Plan can and will be made. The current Action Plan outlines the measures needed to action the CoARA commitments at ZHdK. Over time, we will be able to assess whether the CoARA commitments are being implemented at ZHdK as envisaged while also fitting our organisational culture.

Through the achievement of the milestones, we plan to introduce the ZHdK-members to the CoARA commitments. Further, we want to deepen and develop our qualitative approach to research assessment through reflection and dialogue with the corresponding internal stakeholders on the university and faculty level, as well as share our experience and progress with external stakeholders. By working its Action Plan, ZHdK is seeking to engage all relevant stakeholders in establishing a research evaluation framework aligned with the CoARA principles and to reflect ZHdK's specific values.

The Action Plan is structured based on the actions which ZHdK will implement to further align its research assessment in accordance with the CoARA commitments. For each of the planned actions, the Plan specifies the corresponding CoARA commitment, describes the main objectives, identifies the responsible organisational unit, defines the time frame for achieving the key milestones and states the corresponding output.

Actions	Objectives	Responsible Unit	Milestones	Deliverables	CoARA Commitment
1. Deepen the culture of qualitative research assessment at ZHdK	Define the change to the CoARA commitments as a strategic goal for the Vice-Rectorate for Research and Innovation	University Board	2026	Resources for implementing the Action Plan Internal working group for implementing the Action Plan	5
	Establish an award for diverse and excellent research projects at ZHdK	Research Affairs Office	2027	Award for excellent research projects	1
	Inform ZHdK members about the CoARA initiative and ZHdK's Action Plan	Research Affairs Office	2026	Internal course to introduce CoARA Internal CoARA Action Plan website and newsletter (progress reports)	7
2. Develop and implement field-independent qualitative metrics for excellence in the arts	Establish an interdisciplinary working group	Research Affairs Office	2026	Metrics framework for excellence in the arts	1
	Develop a metrics framework for excellence in the arts	Research Affairs Committee Working Group	2029	Internal course on the usage of the developed metrics for excellence in the arts	3

Actions	Objectives	Responsible Unit	Milestones	Deliverables	CoARA Commitment
3. Abandon the usage of rankings	Publicly announce that rankings will no longer be used	University Board	2026	Public communication	3
	If used, replace ranking-based decisions with the developed metrics for excellence in the arts	Research Affairs Office Research Affairs Committee	2028	Updated decision-making guidelines	4
	Strengthen collaboration with partners who support CoARA	Heads of Departments	2027	New partnerships	4
4. Promote the usage of peer-reviews	Enable ZHdK members to peer review research	Research Affairs Office Research Affairs Committee Teaching & Education Dossier	2029	Guidelines for conducting peer reviews in the arts Regular internal course on peer reviewing in the arts	2
	Establish a permanent peer-review partner for regular peer reviews on institutional level	Research Affairs Office University Development Unit	2029	Partnership with another university	2

Actions	Objectives	Responsible Unit	Milestones	Deliverables	CoARA Commitment
5. Align research assessment tools with CoARA commitments	Develop guidelines to establish whether research assessment tools conform with CoARA commitments	Research Affairs Office Research Affairs Committee	2027	Guidelines on aligning research assessment tools with CoARA commitments	6.1
	Identify all research assessment tools	Research Affairs Office Research Affairs Committee	2026	Updated research assessment tools	6.1 / 6.2
	Check research assessment tools for CoARA conformity		2027		6.1 / 6.2
	Implement CoARA-conform assessment tools where necessary		2029	6.1 / 6.2	
6. Support diverse research career paths	Check requirements of research careers at ZHdK for CoARA conformity	Research Affairs Office	2027	Updated recruitment guidelines	1 / 3
	Revise requirements for research careers at ZHdK for CoARA conformity	Research Affairs Committee Human Resources Management	2028	Define research diversity as a KPI for the research department	6
	Highlight diverse careers, success and impact of ZHdK-researchers based on developed excellence metrics	Research Affairs Office	2029		1 / 3

Actions	Objectives	Responsible Unit	Milestones	Deliverables	CoARA Commitment
7. Provide evidence for beneficial change of the Action Plan	Define clear goals for the objectives of the Action Plan and check results	Working Group	2027	Goal statements for Action Plan objectives	10
	Conduct peer review with other CoARA universities on implementation of Action Plan items	Research Affairs Office Research Affairs Committee	2028	Peer review report	10
	Conduct external evaluation of the implemented Action Plan items	Research Affairs Office Quality Management Unit	2029	External evaluation report	10
8. Support the CoARA initiative	Actively participate in national and international CoARA meetings	Research Affairs Office	2026	Active participation in CoARA meetings (incl. presentations)	8 / 9
	Communicate CoARA membership/support to ZHdK community	Research Affairs Office	2026	Communicate CoARA membership via ZHdK website (incl. Action Plan and other relevant documents)	7 / 8 / 9

The image features a minimalist abstract design. A vertical line in a light blue color runs down the center, intersecting a horizontal line in a dark blue color. To the right of the vertical line, there are two large semi-circular shapes: a dark blue one in the upper right and a medium blue one in the lower right. The background is a light blue color.

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